

TWO FORMULAS FOR SMARANDACHE *LCM* RATIO SEQUENCES

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Abstract In this paper, a reduction formula for Smarandache *LCM* ratio sequences $SLR(6)$ and $SLR(7)$ are given.

Keywords: Smarandache *LCM* ratio sequences; Reduction formula.

§1. Introduction

Let $(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_t)$ and $[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_t]$ denote the greatest common divisor and the least common multiple of any positive integers $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_t$ respectively. Let r be a positive integer with $r > 1$. For any positive integer n , let $T(r, n) = \frac{[n, n+1, \dots, n+r-1]}{[1, 2, \dots, r]}$, then the sequences $SLR(r) = \{T(r, n)\}_\infty$ is called Smarandache *LCM* ratio sequences of degree r . In reference [1], Maohua Le studied the properties of $SLR(r)$, and gave two reduction formulas for $SLR(3)$ and $SLR(4)$. In this paper, we will study the calculating problem of $SLR(6)$ and $SLR(7)$, and prove the following:

Theorem 1. For any positive integer n , we have the following result:

If $n \equiv 0, 15 \pmod{20}$, then

$$SLR(6) = \frac{1}{7200}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5);$$

If $n \equiv 1, 2, 6, 9, 13, 14, 17, 18 \pmod{20}$, then

$$SLR(6) = \frac{1}{720}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5);$$

If $n \equiv 5, 10 \pmod{20}$, then

$$SLR(6) = \frac{1}{3600}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5);$$

If $n \equiv 3, 4, 7, 8, 11, 12, 16, 19 \pmod{20}$, then

$$SLR(6) = \frac{1}{1440}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5).$$

Theorem 2. For any positive integer n , we have the following

If $n \equiv 0, 24, 30, 54 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{302400}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 1, 13, 17, 37, 41, 53 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{5040}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 2, 8, 16, 22, 26, 28, 32, 38, 46, 52, 56, 58 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{20160}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 3, 27, 51 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{30240}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 4, 10, 14, 20, 34, 40, 44, 50 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{100800}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 5, 25, 29, 49 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{25200}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 6, 12, 18, 36, 42, 48 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{60480}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 7, 11, 23, 31, 43, 47 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{10080}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 9, 45 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{75600}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 15, 39 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{151200}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 19, 55, 59, 35 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{50400}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6);$$

If $n \equiv 21, 33, 57 \pmod{60}$, then

$$SLR(7) = \frac{1}{15120}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4)(n+5)(n+6).$$

§2. Proof of the theorem

To complete the proof of Theorem, we need following several simple Lemmas.

Lemma 1. For any positive integer a and b , we have $(a, b)[a, b] = ab$.

Lemma 2. For any positive integer s with $s < t$, we have

$$(x_1, x_2, \dots, x_t) = ((x_1, \dots, x_s), (x_{s+1}, \dots, x_t))$$

and

$$[x_1, x_2, \dots, x_t] = [[x_1, \dots, x_s], [x_{s+1}, \dots, x_t]].$$

Lemma 3. For any positive integer n , we have

$$T(4, n) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{24}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3), & \text{if } n \equiv 1, 2 \pmod{3}; \\ \frac{1}{72}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3), & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{3}. \end{cases}$$

Lemma 4. For any positive integer n , we have

$$T(5, n) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{1440}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4), & \text{if } n \equiv 0, 8 \pmod{12}; \\ \frac{1}{120}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4), & \text{if } n \equiv 1, 7 \pmod{12}; \\ \frac{1}{720}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4), & \text{if } n \equiv 2, 6 \pmod{12}; \\ \frac{1}{360}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4), & \text{if } n \equiv 3, 5, 9, 11 \pmod{12}; \\ \frac{1}{480}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4), & \text{if } n \equiv 4 \pmod{12}; \\ \frac{1}{240}n(n+1)(n+2)(n+3)(n+4), & \text{if } n \equiv 10 \pmod{12}. \end{cases}$$

The proof of Lemma 1 and Lemma 2 can be found in [3], Lemma 3 was proved in [1]. Lemma 4 was proved in [4].

In the following, we shall use these Lemmas to complete the proof of Theorem 1. In fact, from the properties of the least common multiple of any positive integers, we know that

$$\begin{aligned} [n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4, n+5] &= [[n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4], n+5] \\ &= \frac{[n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4](n+5)}{([n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4], n+5)}. \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Note that $[1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6] = 60$, $[1, 2, 3, 4, 5] = 60$ and

$$([n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4], n+5)$$

$$= \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 5, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 0, 20, 30, 50 \pmod{60}; \\ 6, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 1, 13, 31, 49 \pmod{60}; \\ 1, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 2, 6, 8, 12, 14, 18, 24, 26, 32, 38, 42, 44, 48, 54, 56 \pmod{60}; \\ 4, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 3, 11, 23, 27, 39, 47, 51, 59 \pmod{60}; \\ 3, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 4, 16, 22, 28, 34, 46, 52, 58 \pmod{60}; \\ 10, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 5, 45 \pmod{60}; \\ 2, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 9, 17, 21, 29, 33, 41, 53, 57 \pmod{60}; \\ 15, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 10, 40 \pmod{60}; \\ 20, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 15, 35 \pmod{60}; \\ 12, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 7, 19, 31, 43 \pmod{60}; \\ 30, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 25 \pmod{60}; \\ 60, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 55 \pmod{60}. \end{array} \right. \quad (2)$$

Now Theorem 1 follows from Lemma 3.

The proof of Theorem 2 is similar to the proof of Theorem 1. From the properties of the least common multiple of any positive integers, we know that

$$\begin{aligned} & [n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4, n+5, n+6] \\ &= [[n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4, n+5], n+6] \\ &= \frac{[n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4, n+5](n+6)}{([n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4, n+5], n+6)}. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Note that $[1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7] = 420$, and

$$([n, n+1, n+2, n+3, n+4, n+5], n+6) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} 6, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 0, 12, 36, 48 \pmod{60}; \\ 1, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 1, 5, 7, 11, 13, 17, 23, 25, 31, 35, 37, 41, 43, 47, 53, 55 \pmod{60}; \\ 4, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 2, 10, 22, 26, 38, 46, 50, 58 \pmod{60}; \\ 3, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 3, 15, 21, 27, 33, 45, 51, 57 \pmod{60}; \\ 10, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 4, 44 \pmod{60}; \\ 12, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 6, 18, 30, 42 \pmod{60}; \\ 2, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 8, 16, 20, 28, 32, 40, 52, 56 \pmod{60}; \\ 15, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 9, 39 \pmod{60}; \\ 20, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 14, 34 \pmod{60}; \\ 5, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 19, 29, 49, 59 \pmod{60}; \\ 30, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 24 \pmod{60}; \\ 60, \quad \text{if } n \equiv 54 \pmod{60}. \end{array} \right. \quad (4)$$

Now Theorem 2 follows from Theorem 1.

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